

Modeling low-carbon energy pathways : Case of Senegal

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Context, Challenges, and Main Findings

- Senegal is facing major energy challenges linked to the exploitation of hydrocarbon resources (oil and gas) and meeting its climate commitments.
- In addition, Senegal recently signed the **JETP** agreement, aim of achieving a **40% electricity mix by 2030**.

Given the availability of fossil fuels, could the country achieve an electricity mix with of 40% of RE ?

Can the country stop investing in the development of fossil-fired power stations from 2050 ?

Electricity capacity total Installed, 2022

Scenarios

BAU

Baseline scenario, reflecting the country's current energy situation.

This trend will be extended to 2050 without any additional measures. Energy supply and demand increase in an exponential fashion.

JETP

Reflects the Senegalese government's commitments under the recently signed JETP agreement.

It targets a **40% penetration rate of renewable energies in electricity production in 2030.**

LoWC

Low carbon scenario promotes the use of cleaner and sustainable energy sources to meet demand in different sectors.

No more investment in fossil-fuel power plan in 2050 (coal, NG, HFO, etc.).

Installed capacity

Power generation

Total Emission

Total cost

Policy insight

- Implementing the JETP and LoWC scenarios will require substantial investment, in excess of **US\$14m each**. This will require concerted efforts from **all stakeholders** (government, private sector, financial partners, investment banks, etc.).

- The current context of **oil and gas exploitation** should not limit the application of these scenarios. The financial resources generated by the exploitation of oil and gas reserves **should be used to implement these scenarios**.

- Given the high cost of storage and the intermittent nature of renewables, it is recommended that gas-fired power plan be available over the long term to offset disruptions and maintain a trend towards reducing greenhouse gas emissions, while waiting to develop sufficient storage capacity for renewables.

Future work

Data review and update

Storage modelling

Explore another scenarios aimed at increasing the use of natural gas in productive sectors.

Thanks you